
ALTERNATIVE ENERGY SOURCE

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PUERTO PRINCESA CITY'S PATH TO SUSTAINABILITY: SOLAR POWER AS ALTERNATIVE ENERGY SOURCE

Puerto Princesa City is known for its tourist and geographical attractions. Whereby not only having a yield from it but also establishing an identity towards other places. Due to the overuse of fossil fuels, Puerto Princesa's tourist and geographical sites are gradually being harmed, which is why there is a need for clean, renewable energy sources. Hossain stated that extensive use of fossil fuels results in global warming, which in turn causes a rise in temperatures, a change in the pattern of rainfall, and an increase in the levels of ocean water (Hossain). Sunlight is highly present almost year-round here in Puerto

Image from the City Government of Puerto Princesa City

Princesa City alone; as a result, solar energy stands out as the better alternative to conventional energy resources such as burning fossil fuels. Lahiri stated that by investing more in solar energy, we will not only create an efficient alternative energy source but also take a significant change into reducing our reliance on fossil fuels (Lahiri). Further cutting out greenhouse gas emissions and overall providing a safer environment for people to live in.

BUT WHY SOLAR ENERGY?

Solar energy is simply the most accessible as well as renewable energy source that is highly available here in Puerto Princesa City, to a point where people here complain about the heat even during September to December, where the climate is usually colder. According to Al-Ezzi, this uses the present sunlight to create electricity through photovoltaic (PV) cells, generating electricity without producing any harmful byproducts (Al-Ezzi). With all the clear skies and lots of sunlight Puerto Princesa City has, implementing solar energy as an alternative source of energy provides

us an efficient and cost-effective solution to reach our energy demand.

Image from Philippine Star

RAW MATERIALS AND TECHNOLOGY NEEDED

According to an article from Maysun Solar, the main components of a solar energy system are the following (Brian):

- **Solar Panel:** Photovoltaic cells that catch sunlight and convert it into electricity.
 - ✓ Solar Panel Glass
 - ✓ Solar Panel Encapsulation Film
 - ✓ Solar Cell
 - ✓ Solar Panel Back sheet / Back Glass
 - ✓ Solar Panel Frame
 - ✓ Solar Panel Junction Box (J-Box)
- **Inverters:** Device that converts the electricity generated from direct current (DC) into alternating current (AC).
- **Batteries:** Although listed as optional, they are advisable for storing surplus energy for emergency situations.
- **Mounting Structures:** These are essential for securely attaching the panels to surfaces, which are usually rooftops or open fields.
- **Wiring and Monitoring Systems:** Necessary for the system to function correctly and to monitor its performance.

Fortunately, these materials are easily accessible right here in Puerto Princesa City, and thanks to technological advancements, their costs have dropped significantly over the years.

AREA REQUIREMENTS

Setting up a solar energy system requires us a big enough space to install the solar panels. Gupta stated that on average, a 1-kilowatt (kW) solar panel system needs about 10 square meters of area (Gupta). For a community as big as Puerto Princesa City, let's assume that we need about 50 houses to be powered. That would need about 500 square meters of area for the solar panels, producing 50 kilowatts (kW), enough to power 50 households. Open fields, school or mall rooftops, and free public spaces that are not used properly in Puerto Princesa City could serve as ideal locations for such installations. Like the plains of Rancho in Santa Monica, abandoned squatter areas in certain bay areas of Puerto Princesa City, or even the rooftops of NCCC Mall, SM Mall, and Robinson's Mall.

Image from Travel Tripsters

COST OF ESTABLISHMENT

For Puerto Princesa City, a 50-kilowatt (kW) system is enough to power about 50 households. This would approximately cost about **PHP 4,000,000 to PHP 5,000,000**. All including the cost of the panels, inverters, batteries, mounting structures, wiring, and monitoring systems, as well as the installation. Although, yes, the capital seems quite a lot, but I guarantee you, the system's lifespan of 20–25 years and possible high savings on electricity bills outweigh the present overusage of fossil fuels, which will certainly doom our environment. Undoubtedly, the government should be the one to act, but still, we can provide our ideas as well as funds for our sustainable future.

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